

CART and CHAID ANALYSIS

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Classification and Regression Trees (CART) and Chi Square Automatic Interaction Detector (CHAID) works on principles of decision tree analysis. Classification and Regression (CART) classifies the data based on the categorical outcome variable (Classification) and also uses continuous outcome variable for regression problem. Chi Square Automatic Interaction Detector (CHAID) is similar to CART which uses classifies the data into multiple class labels not only binary classification. In CHAID both dependent variable and independent variables will be categorical. This paper provides an overview and CART and CHAID methods using open source R software with hypothetical data set

Keywords: Decision Tree, Classification, Regression, CART, CHAID

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